

Ethyl 3, 4, 5-Trimethoxy Benzoate from *Anacardium occidentale* Gum

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In continuation of our detailed chemical examination^{1,2} of different parts of *Anacardium occidentale* (Anacardiaceae) we have studied the pale yellow gum obtained from mature trees and our results are recorded here.

The dry gum (200 g.) in coarse powder form was exhaustively extracted with ether and acetone in succession. The ether extract on concentration yielded a small quantity of a colourless solid, which when crystallised from methanol came out as needles, m.p. 53–54° (Found : C, 60.1, H, 6.7, C₁₂H₁₆O₅ requires C, 60.0, H, 6.6%). More of this was obtained on pouring the acetone concentrate to ice-cold water (yield, 0.3 g.). The compound was soluble in hot benzene, ether, acetone and methanol and very sparingly in cold water. It did not give any colour with alc. Fe³⁺ or aq. NaOH. On hydrolysis with 4*N* NaOH and subsequent acidification, a colourless crystalline solid was obtained which after recrystallisation from ether came out as needles, m.p. 166–68° (Found : C, 56.4, H, 5.6, OMe, 40.6; C₁₀H₁₂O₅ requires C, 56.6, H, 5.7, 3 OMe, 43.8%). This was esterified (MeOH + conc. H₂SO₄; 100°, 1 hr.) and the excess acid neutralised with NaHCO₃. The methyl ester extracted with ether, on recrystallisation from benzene-methanol came out as colourless needles, m.p. 82–83° (Found : C, 58.5, H, 6.3, OMe, 51.5; C₁₁H₁₄O₅ requires C, 58.4, H, 6.1 and 4 OMe, 54.8%). This was identified as methyl 3,4,5-trimethoxy benzoate and the acid as 3,4,5-trimethoxy benzoic acid.

The aqueous layer containing the alcohol formed during hydrolysis was distilled on a boiling water bath before ether extraction and in the distillate ethanol was identified.

From the above data, the original compound was identified as ethyl 3,4,5-trimethoxy benzoate³ (ethyl gallate trimethyl ether). The identity was finally established by direct comparison, co-TLC and m.m.p. determination with authentic ethyl gallate trimethyl ether synthesised from gallic acid by esterification (EtOH + conc. H₂SO₄, 100°) and subsequent methylation (Me₂SO₄ + K₂CO₃ in Me₂CO, 20 hr.).

The ether and acetone mother liquors gave violet colour with alc. Fe³⁺ and on PC and TLC was found to contain traces of ethyl gallate.

1. S. S. Subramanian, K. J. Joseph and A. G. R. Nair, *Phytochem.*, 1969, **8**, 673.
2. S. S. Subramanian and A. G. R. Nair, *Curr. Sci.*, 1969, **38**, 494.
3. G. Harris, *Dictionary of Organic Compounds*, 4th Ed., Vol. III, Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1965, 1494.

This is the first record of isolation of ethyl 3,4,5-trimethoxy benzoate from a natural source. It is biogenetically interesting that the leaves and flowers¹ of *A. occidentale* are rich in ethyl gallate while the seed coat² contains high proportion of catechins and the gum ethyl gallate trimethyl ether.

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